

EasyUnicode Key Mapping Chart

EasyUnicode is a Keyboard layout file for Mac OS X (10.2 or later) to type Unicode characters for basic Sanskrit/Pali transcription.

*For transcription, I simply follow the International Alphabet of Sanskrit Transliteration (IAST) which is based on a standard established by the International Congress of Orientalists at Geneva in 1894 (See *Grammaire Sanscrite*, by Louis Renou, Tome 1, pp. xi-xiii, 1968). Although I have come across some different opinions requesting, for example, *ʃ* or *ʒ* in place of *ṣ*, I think we still have good reason to stick to the IAST.

1. To type characters with diacritical marks for basic Sanskrit/Pali transcription, please use the combination with "option" key.

Chart ("option" key):

esc	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
⌘	©	○	§	×	†	ॐ	<	>	∅	-	~	!	⌘
→	˘	-	ē	ṛ	ṭ	¥	ū	ī	ō			‘	↶
^	ā	ś	ḍ	ṝ	ṇ̄	ḥ	ñ̄	ṇ̄	ḷ	ḻ		’	
⏶	ž	ṣ	ñ̄	√	ʰ	ṇ̄	ṃ	ṃ	...	•			⏶
⏶	⌘	⌘	英数					かな	⌘	⌘	⌘	^	

Examples:

ā: Opt+a, ū: Opt+u, ṇ̄: Opt+k or g.

2. For capital characters, add "shift" key to the above combination.

Chart ("option+shift" key):

esc	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13	
	®	©		※	‡	⦿	«	»	∅	—			⌘	
→	≈	≈	Ē	Ṛ	Ṭ		Ū	Ī	Ō			“	“	↶
^	Ā	Ś	Ḍ	Ṝ	Ṇ̄	Ḥ	Ñ̄	Ṇ̄	Ḷ	ḻ		”		
⏶	Ž	Ṣ	Ñ̄		ʰ	Ṇ̄	Ṅ	Ṅ		◦			⏶	
⏶	⌘	⌘	英数					かな	⌘	⌘	⌘	^		

Examples:

Ā: Opt+Shift+a, Ṛ: Opt+Shift+r, Ś: Opt+Shift+x.

3. To type French and German special characters, please use the combination with "option+control" key.

Chart ("option+control" key):

esc	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
									ø				⊗
→	æ	è	é	ê	ô	ä	ü	ï	ö	ë	œ		↶
^	à	ù	â	î	û								
↑	ß		ç			η		,	.	/	_		↑
☰	∖	⌘	英数						かな	⌘	∖		^

Examples:

É: Opt+control+e, ù: Opt+control+u.

4. For capital characters, add "shift" key to the above combination.

Chart ("option+control+shift" key):

esc	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13
									ø				⊗
→	Æ	È	É	Ê	Ô	Ä	Ü	Ï	Ö	Ë	Œ		↶
^	À	Ù	Â	Î	Û								
↑			Ç										↑
☰	∖	⌘	英数						かな	⌘	∖		^

Examples:

É: Opt+control+shift+e, Ç: Opt+control+shift+c.

5. EasyUnicode keyboard also provides other "Unicode Combining Diacritical Marks" (0301-0362). To add any of them to any of letters, first type the letter to which you wish to add a diacritical mark, then press "option+1" to call for keys for diacritical marks (see the chart below), then press the key assigned for the mark you wish to add.

For example, you can add acute accent mark "´" on the letter "ã" by:

